

From Beans to Tourism: Exploring the Potential of Coffee-Based Tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: Global tourism trends are predicted to continue to increase year after year. Sustainable and eco-friendly tourism is predicted to become a relevant trend, as tourists' awareness of the importance of authentic experiences increases. Agrotourism is one form of tourism that reflects these values. In Indonesia, coffee-based tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu has great potential to be developed as sustainable coffee tourism. The advantages of nature, culture, and distinctive local coffee make them aligned with the trend of authentic and eco-friendly tourism. This study aims to explore the potential, strengths, challenges, and opportunities for developing coffee tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu. The method used is a descriptive qualitative approach with a comparative case study strategy. The research results show that coffee tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu has significant potential for development as nature, culture, and community-based destinations. The geographical characteristics, unique local coffee, and active community participation support the development of sustainable tourism based on Community-Based Tourism (CBT). Challenges such as human resources, infrastructure, and promotion can be addressed through training, product diversification, and cross-stakeholder collaboration.

KEYWORDS: coffee-based tourism, agrotourism, community-based tourism, sustainable tourism.

1. INTRODUCTION

The World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) stated that the global Travel and Tourism sector is projected to grow rapidly by 2025, reaffirming its role as a cornerstone of the world's major economies. In 2024, the travel and tourism sector contributed approximately 10% to the global economy, with a total value of \$10.9 trillion. This value increased 8.5% compared to the previous year. This year, the WTTC projects that the travel and tourism sector will contribute \$11.7 trillion to the global economy, or approximately 10.3% of total global GDP. This contribution is predicted to increase by 2035 to \$16.5 trillion, equivalent to 11.5% of global GDP (WTTC, 2025). This condition indicates that the global trend of the travel and tourism sector will continue.

In Indonesia itself, tourism trends are projected to continue growing year after year. Data from the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy/*Kemenparekraf* (*Kemenparekraf*, 2024) shows that this increase is primarily driven by tourist interest in cultural experiences, health and wellness tourism, and ecotourism, or environmentally-based tourism. Furthermore, *Kemenparekraf* also predicts that future tourism trends will be dominated by outdoor activities and adventure, specifically vacations to destinations with cool climates (mountains, lakes, and forests). In May 2025, the Indonesian Ministry of Tourism (2025) recorded 97,673,863 domestic tourist trips. This figure increased compared to 82,909,661 trips in May 2024. The majority of domestic tourist trips were to West Java, East Java, and Central Java.

In August 2024, *Kemenparekraf* launched the "Keep The Wonder" campaign as an effort to preserve nature, culture, and traditions in Indonesia while continuing to develop the tourism sector. Tourism that promotes environmentally friendly and sustainable concepts is expected to become a relevant tourism trend. This aligns with increasing tourist awareness of the importance of authentic experiences and sustainable practices. One form of authentic tourism concept that prioritizes sustainable practices (*sustainable tourism*) is agrotourism. Agrotourism is a combination of agricultural activities and rural tourism that can contribute to rural socio-economic development and has traditional values such as respect for culture, traditions, lifestyle, and authenticity (McGehee & Kim, 2004; Vukolić et. al., 2023). Agrotourism is a form of rural tourism that not only opens up new sources of income for local businesses but also encourages community involvement in preserving their region's natural resources and culture. Agrotourism also serves as a strategy for realizing sustainable rural development based on local potential (Susila et. at, 2024; Kothari & Perwej, 2021). Coffee-based agrotourism or coffee-based tourism is part of rural tourism and a branch of agrotourism based on the coffee sector, encompassing aspects of consumption, history, traditions, products, and culture inherent in a region (Uwimana & Uwimpuhwe, 2022). Dinis et. al. (2021) stated that coffee tourism encourages direct tourist involvement in various coffee-related activities. These activities generally include visits to coffee plantations to learn about the history, harvesting, selection, and processing of coffee beans, as well as enjoying tasting sessions, shopping for processed products, and even coffee-based souvenirs. The development of coffee tourism has quite complex impacts on tourist destinations. Overall, this tourism concept has a more dominant positive impact than negative. Coffee tourism contributes to expanding economic and cultural diversity, supporting the marketing of local commodities, increasing employment opportunities for the community, building a positive destination image, encouraging regional economic growth, and playing a role in improving the welfare of local residents (Pan, 2023).

From Beans to Tourism: Exploring the Potential of Coffee-Based Tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu, Indonesia

The positive contribution of the coffee-based tourism sector has been proven to improve the welfare of local communities in the region of coffee-based tourism in various countries. In Yunnan Province, China, coffee tourism has become a distinctive identity, significantly increasing tourist visits and driving economic and social development. Before the development of coffee tourism, Yunnan's economy lagged behind other coastal provinces in China. However, with the arrival of high-speed rail and tourism promotion, the coffee industry has grown rapidly through recreational agricultural tourism (Pan, 2023). Coffee-based tourism also has the potential to increase coffee production, improve farmer welfare, and strengthen the coffee sector in Rwanda, as it motivates farmers to improve their agricultural practices (Uwimana & Uwimpuhwe, 2022). Meanwhile, in Indonesia, the development of coffee-based tourism has had a positive impact on coffee tourism managers in Rigin Jaya, West Lampung, through economic growth, strengthening social ties, and fostering concern for environmental sustainability (Umaryani et al., 2023). The development of coffee agrotourism also increases employment opportunities for the people of Colol Village, East Lamba Leda District, East Manggarai Regency, East Nusa Tenggara, including changes in household income and social changes in rural communities for a better life (Nalo et al., 2023).

Coffee-based tourism practices in Indonesia that have great potential for development, includes coffee tourism in Posong, Temanggung Regency, and Sekipan, Tawangmangu District, Karanganyar Regency. Both locations are located in Central Java Province. In line with tourist visit data in Indonesia, where Central Java ranks third as the most visited province, the potential for coffee-based agrotourism in these two locations is very likely to develop rapidly. Pan (2023) argues that the launch of comprehensive regional coffee-themed tourism development will encourage the comprehensive development of coffee-producing regions and inject new vitality into the development of the coffee industry. Posong is a tourist area in Tlahab Village, Kledung District, Temanggung Regency, which offers natural beauty and views of Mount Sindoro and Mount Sumbing as main tourist destinations. In addition, Posong is also known for its high-quality processed coffee products, most of which are cultivated using a diversified pattern of coffee and tobacco plants, resulting in a distinctive flavor. This cultivation diversification practice is one of the activities offered by agrotourism. On the other hand, Tawangmangu District, Karanganyar Regency, located on the slopes of Mount Lawu, is developing as a unique coffee tourism destination thanks to its rich environment and culture. The main production is Arabica coffee at altitudes of 1,200–1,800 meters above sea level and a small amount of Robusta in the lower elevations. This is supported by natural planting methods and tourism activities such as nature walks and traditional ceremonies, creating a sustainable and authentic tourism experience. Thus, the development of coffee tourism in Posong and Sekipan not only has bright prospects in terms of tourist attraction but also aligns with the direction of tourism development that encourages local economic growth and revitalization of the coffee industry.

Therefore, this article aims to explore the potential for coffee-based tourism development in two destinations: Posong, Temanggung Regency, and Sekipan, Tawangmangu, Karanganyar Regency. Furthermore, this article aims to identify the strengths, challenges, and opportunities for developing these two coffee tourism destinations. Support for the development of these two coffee tourism destinations is expected to be a strategic step towards establishing the Posong and Sekipan coffee-producing areas as leading, sustainable agrotourism centers in Indonesia.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

a. Coffee-Based Tourism Concept

Coffee-based tourism is a form of thematic tourism that emphasizes experiences surrounding coffee, from cultivation and harvesting to processing, to serving and drinking. This concept combines aspects of agrotourism, culinary arts, local culture, and education, and is often integrated with elements of ecotourism and local communities. According to Uwimana & Uwimpuhe (2022) coffee-based tourism is related to coffee consumption, history, traditions, products, and culture of a destination. This type of tourism is very popular in coffee-producing regions and is suitable for tourists who want to experience coffee culture firsthand. Several forms of coffee-based tourism exist, including coffee agrotourism, coffee and local culture, coffee classes or workshops, coffee festivals or events, and so on. Coffee-based tourism is closely related to coffee farming or plantations. According to studies Wafaretta & Faronny (2024) which underscores the important role of sustainable agricultural practices in increasing economic benefits while preserving local ecosystems. His research on coffee educational tourism focuses on tourists who will further deepen their knowledge and increase interest in Liberica coffee, in addition to interactive classes. In addition, this coffee educational tourism can be implemented in coffee plantation areas or outside the coffee plantation area by collaborating with coffee shops or coffee shops around the tourist location. Coffee-based tourism is a part of rural tourism that is believed to have begun in the late 19th century in Hawaii, where coffee is part of the luxurious vegetation in the highlands, where some tourists have travel experiences related to coffee in the region (Woyesa & Kumar, 2021; Uwimana & Uwimpuhwe, 2022).

The coffee farming sector is influenced by two main factors: fluctuating international coffee prices depending on the current situation. On the other hand, agricultural input costs fluctuate due to inflation and other related factors. These factors negatively impact coffee farming profitability, causing some farmers to lose motivation. Therefore, innovative solutions are needed to address this issue. According to Wafaretta & Faronny (2025), coffee-based tourism is considered a growing tourism niche market and could provide solutions to the problems facing the coffee sector. Meanwhile, Uwimana & Uwimpuhe (2022) argue that the core issue is that coffee-based rural tourism will increase community incomes and may reverse the expansion of agriculture into sensitive forests. Several academics have emphasized the importance of culinary tourism in developed and certain developing countries to enhance consumption-related products (e.g., wine, beer, rice, and tea), and various efforts have been made to study the drivers and threats of tourism in developing countries. Casalegno et al. (2020) little research has been conducted on the potential for developing tourism activities centered on coffee producers and their plantations in equatorial countries to determine whether a coffee tourism market is developing in these locations and whether this could enhance the brand perception of these countries.

From Beans to Tourism: Exploring the Potential of Coffee-Based Tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu, Indonesia

Concepts that can be applied in development of Coffee-Based Tourism can be developed independently or combined depending on the character of the region, coffee potential, and the carrying capacity of the local community. Some examples of concepts that can be implemented include 1) Coffee Agro-Tourism, which focuses on education and direct interaction with the coffee cultivation process. The main activities are guided coffee plantation tours, direct coffee harvesting (seasonal), post-harvest demonstrations (fermentation, drying, roasting), and learning about coffee varieties and cultivation techniques. This concept is suitable for active coffee-producing areas. 2) Coffee Education Tourism, which focuses on increasing knowledge about coffee from upstream to downstream. Activities carried out include: workshop manual coffee brewing (V60, Chemex, French press, etc.), basic barista and latte art training, cupping (coffee tasting) training, presentations or documentaries about local coffee. This is suitable for school activities, communities, students, or educational tourists. 3) Creative Coffee Tourism, which focuses on combining coffee with creativity and digital content. Its main activities include providing thematic coffee photo spots (instagrammable), local coffee festivals or coffee MSME bazaars, creative content classes (vlogs, coffee food photography), themed cafes and co-working space. This concept is very suitable to be applied to the younger generation, the creator community and as a tourist city. 4) Coffee Culinary Tourism, this concept focuses on exploring the taste of coffee and its accompanying food. Activities carried out include coffee pairing (coffee + local food or dessert), demonstrations of making coffee-based products (coffee ice cream, spiced coffee, etc.), tours of legendary coffee shops & contemporary coffee shops, competitions or innovative coffee drink festivals. This concept is suitable to be applied in urban areas or cities with a strong culinary trend such as Bandung, Yogyakarta, and Malang. These concepts are some of the existing concepts and have been implemented in several regions. A combination of concepts can also be done as needed to increase the selling power of coffee-based tourism.

Implementation of Coffee-Based Tourism in countries in the world such as 1) Coffee Cultural Landscape – Colombia, 2) Blue Mountain Coffee Tour – Jamaica, 3) Coffee Farm Experience – Ethiopia, 4) Kona Coffee *Living History* Farm– Hawaii, United States and so on. While the implementation Coffee-Based Tourism in Indonesia, there are still only a few, including 1) Banaran Coffee Village in Semarang, Central Java, 2) Kintamani Coffee in Bali, 3) Malasari Tourism Village in Bogor, West Java, 4) Rigis Jaya Coffee Village in West Lampung, and 5) Toraja Coffee Trail in South Sulawesi. This is not comparable to the large number of coffee plantations in Indonesia. Coffee-based tourism has enormous potential and benefits for development. The potential and benefits of coffee-based tourism include: 1) Improving the local economy and coffee farmers; 2) Preserving local coffee and surrounding culture; 3) Encouraging sustainable tourism; and 4) Raising awareness of quality and fair coffee (*fair trade*).

The Setiyorini study (2019) stated that tourism development is being utilized by many countries to improve social welfare. Tourism often synergizes with various sectors to enhance its benefits, such as agrotourism, which utilizes agricultural resources for tourism activities. Coffee is a leading agricultural commodity in Indonesia, and there are extensive plantations in many areas. The facilities and resources available on plantations have the potential to provide higher economic value for local communities (Anbalagan & Lovelock, 2014). Therefore, developing coffee tourism can provide added value to local communities; as a result, their well-being has the potential to improve. The study identified positive social impacts of tourism as increasing resident engagement in cultural activities, providing more entertainment, increasing a region's global visibility, creating an image, enhancing understanding of local heritage, fostering mutual understanding of cultural differences, and providing more opportunities to learn about other countries (Setyorini, 2018). Meanwhile, negative impacts include uncontrolled development, impacts on local cultural identity, decreased community cohesion, increased crime, prostitution, vandalism, and conflicts between residents and visitors, as well as decreased security in local communities. These interactions will both influence and be influenced by culture. Culture can attract visitors to tourist destinations, and tourism development, in some cases, can also contribute to these impacts.

Meanwhile, coffee-based tourism faces various challenges. These challenges include: 1) Dependence on the Harvest Season, 2) Limited Accessibility and Infrastructure, 3) Lack of Human Resource Capacity (Farmers & Guides), 4) Risk of Destructive Commercialization, 4) Climate Change & Production Crisis, 5) Lack of Service Standards and Tourism Protocols. Furthermore, other challenges will arise, particularly in institutional terms, tourism product packaging, the availability of supporting facilities, and empowering local communities. To address these challenges, a comprehensive improvement strategy is needed, ranging from strengthening institutional capacity, innovation in tourism packages, development of basic infrastructure, to increasing active community participation in every management process (Suwarti & Aryaningtyas, 2025). Besides the challenges, there are major obstacles in developing coffee-based tourism, especially in Indonesia, which are often faced by business actors, communities, and local governments.

b. Socio-Economic Added Value of Coffee-Based Tourism

Coffee-based tourism is a form of thematic tourism that leverages the appeal of coffee, including its cultivation, processing, drinking culture, and the natural scenery of coffee plantations. This type of tourism is increasingly developing in various coffee-producing regions, such as Indonesia (e.g., Toraja, Gayo, Kintamani, and West Java). The agricultural industry, also known as agro-industry, plays a significant role in increasing the added value of agricultural commodities, providing productive employment, and generating foreign exchange (Wuryantoro et al., 2022). The role of the agricultural sector is not only seen in terms of the primary products it produces, but must also be linked to the processing and marketing industries it creates and its role in attracting and encouraging development, particularly in rural areas. According to Udayana in Wuryantoro et al. (2022), agroindustry is an industry that processes and transforms primary agricultural products into semi-finished or finished goods with added value and ready for consumption. Coffee-based tourism has added socioeconomic value because it focuses not only on coffee as a commodity, but also on the process, culture, and community behind it. This creates new economic opportunities while strengthening local social structures. Increasing land productivity for Liberica coffee cultivation through support from local groups and governments through the creation of agricultural product-based tourism villages can boost the local economy. Furthermore, optimizing cultivation activities by creating added value through strengthening capital is crucial (Rizkiyah & Shofiyah, 2021). There are socio-economic added values from coffee-based tourism, including the following:

From Beans to Tourism: Exploring the Potential of Coffee-Based Tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu, Indonesia

1) Economic Added Value

a. Diversification of Income Sources

Coffee farmers rely not only on selling their beans but also generate income from farm tours, selling processed products, and providing educational tourism. Local MSMEs (such as cafes, homestays, and handicrafts) are also thriving.

b. Product Value Enhancement

Tourists are often attracted to products with a local story or uniqueness, so attractively packaged local coffee associated with the travel experience can command a premium price. Education about specialty coffee can raise awareness of quality, leading to higher selling prices.

c. Creating New Jobs

Tourism activities create demand for tour guides, local baristas, craftsmen, accommodation, local transportation, and so on.

2) Social Added Value

a. Local Community Empowerment

Coffee tourism encourages active community involvement in managing local potential, thereby fostering a sense of ownership and participation. Women and young people often find new opportunities in this tourism sector.

b. Preservation of Culture and Local Wisdom

Coffee drinking traditions, traditional farming methods, and the history of coffee in a region can be preserved through tourism. Local coffee festivals, coffee workshops, or experiences staying in a farmer's home provide cultural education.

c. Knowledge Exchange

Interaction between tourists and local communities can enrich the insights of both parties, both in aspects of sustainable agriculture, culture, and small business management.

Meanwhile, this coffee-based tourism concept has a positive impact on the environment (socio-economic). Sawerah et al. (2025) shows that farmers' understanding of the benefits and added value of coffee plantation agrotourism activities has increased, and an agrotourism package has been created, including visitors seeing coffee plantations, picking coffee cherries, planting coffee, and observing the roasting process. Community-based and authentic experience-oriented coffee tourism often promotes organic or sustainable farming, maintaining biodiversity, and caring for the natural landscape, as the environment becomes part of the tourist attraction. Examples of real practices in Indonesia include 1) Kintamani, Bali, a coffee tourism village that combines visits to plantations, post-harvest processes, and enjoying coffee in natural scenery. This tourism attracts international tourists and increases farmers' incomes. 2) Gayo, Aceh, which is an educational tour of organic coffee and the local culture of the Gayo community, helping to strengthen regional identity as well as a new economic source. Coffee-based tourism is not only about enjoying coffee, but also about building a locally based creative economic ecosystem that is inclusive, sustainable, and strengthens the socio-cultural identity of coffee-producing communities. According to Rizkiyah & Shofiyah (2021), mastery of technology as a driver for the realization of added value in agricultural businesses as well as to increase competitiveness.

c. Integrating Coffee Cultivation with Tourism

This integration is a combination of coffee farming (cultivation) activities with tourism activities, so that visitors not only enjoy coffee, but also learn, experience firsthand the cultivation process, and understand the lives of farmers and local culture. The purpose of integrating coffee cultivation with tourism is to increase the economic value of coffee cultivation activities, as a promotion of local coffee as a regional specialty, provide education to tourists about the coffee process from upstream to downstream, create jobs in rural areas through the tourism sector, encourage environmental preservation and local culture. In addition, mentoring, counseling, business capital and marketing assistance are needed to ensure that there is no conversion of forest land to other uses and increase the added value of community coffee products (Juningsih & Widiyanto, 2024). One alternative to increasing coffee production is to integrate coffee farming with tourism. Examples of integrated coffee cultivation and tourism, which combine coffee farming activities with educational, cultural, and recreational tourism experiences, include the following:

- 1) **Planting and tending coffee**, with tourist activities participating in planting coffee seeds and learning farming techniques, especially coffee.
- 2) **Coffee harvest**, Activities such as coffee harvest tours or tourists picking coffee cherries.
- 3) **Post-harvest (Wet/dry process, roasting)**, conducting coffee processing workshops and holding cupping classes.
- 4) **View of the coffee plantation**, for example, tracking, glamping and also landscape photography in coffee plantations.
- 5) **Farmhouse**, such as homestay and living experience with coffee farmers.
- 6) **Coffee drinking culture**, The activities include coffee tasting, traditional coffee drinking rituals, and coffee culture.

According to Saprina et al. (2022), one effort that can be made to increase coffee production and tourist locations efficiently is by integrating coffee tourism with coffee plants. Meanwhile, the benefits of integrating coffee cultivation with tourism (coffee agritourism) can be seen from various aspects, namely 1) Economic benefits: increased farmer income and derivative business opportunities (e.g. cafes, souvenirs, and tourism services) 2) Social benefits: can empower communities and strengthen local identity and culture 3) Environmental benefits: to encourage sustainable agriculture and preservation of the surrounding natural landscape. In addition, there are several keys to the success of coffee cultivation integration including 1) Local community involvement – residents as the main actors in tourism; 2) Human resource training – tour guides, local baristas, and hospitality; 3) Supporting facilities – tourist routes, accommodation, coffee education places; 4) Digital marketing – coffee tourism promotion through social media, websites, and so on; 5) Multi-stakeholder collaboration – farmers, cooperatives, village governments, tourism actors, and the private sector. The integration of coffee cultivation and tourism will be successful if it is community-based, equipped with training and facilities, and managed professionally with a collaborative and sustainable spirit. Based on the study Juningsih & Widiyanto (2024) have shown that developing coffee using agroforestry methods is environmentally friendly compared to other

From Beans to Tourism: Exploring the Potential of Coffee-Based Tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu, Indonesia

land uses such as monoculture farming. While it contributes to farmers' incomes, coffee cultivation has not yet become a primary source of income for the majority of farmers.

d. The Role of Local Communities and Empowerment: Community-Based Tourism (CBT)

A local community is a group of people living in a specific geographic area (such as a village, hamlet, or specific area) who have social, cultural, and economic ties, and share common values, norms, and goals. In the context of Community-Based Tourism (CBT), local communities play a crucial role as managers, cultural protectors, and beneficiaries who must be empowered and actively involved. Furthermore, local communities are at the heart of Community-Based Tourism (CBT). Without the active involvement and empowerment of local communities, tourism will not be sustainable. Successful Community-Based Tourism (CBT) positions the community as the owner, primary actor, and primary beneficiary of tourism activities.

Community-Based Tourism (CBT) is a form of tourism managed and owned by local communities, with the goal of providing direct benefits to the local population while preserving culture and the environment. In this approach, the community is not merely a tourist attraction, but an active participant in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of tourism activities. According to Utami et al. (2022) shows that the implementation of Community-Based Tourism (CBT) from an economic and social aspect in a region provides benefits and positive impacts, such as the creation of jobs, new income for the community, improved quality of life, increased pride in the community, and the willingness and loyalty of the community to be involved in every activity in a region so that the development of tourist villages can be sustainable.

The role of local communities and empowerment in Community-Based Tourism (CBT) includes the following:

a. Tourism Activity Managers and Implementers

The community is directly involved in managing attractions, accommodations, transportation, and tour packages. These communities serve as tour guides, artisans, artists, and homestay owners.

b. Conservation of Culture and Nature

Community-Based Tourism (CBT) supports the preservation of local culture (dance, music, food, and customs) as a tourist attraction. Communities also protect local natural ecosystems, such as forests, beaches, or traditional agriculture.

c. Decision maker

Communities are involved in deliberations to determine the direction of tourism development, so that decisions reflect local values and needs.

d. Economic Beneficiaries

Income from tourism is directly enjoyed by residents, improving their economic well-being.

Meanwhile, empowerment in Community-Based Tourism (CBT) is the process of increasing the capacity of communities to actively and independently participate in Community-Based Tourism (CBT). Candelo et. al. (2019) shows that empowerment and collaboration, business diversification, sustainability, and destination image creation are the four main benefits for local farming communities and their families and are also considered to create favorable and attractive conditions for tourists. Some categories of empowerment in Community-Based Tourism (CBT) include:

- a. **Economic Empowerment namely** creating new job opportunities (homestay, culinary, crafts, guiding) and encouraging local entrepreneurship.
- b. **Social Empowerment, namely** increasing the community's sense of self-confidence and independence, strengthening solidarity and cooperation between residents.
- c. **Education Empowerment and Capacity** namely skills training (foreign languages, hospitality, tourism management) and outreach on conservation, sanitation and tourism safety.
- d. **Political Empowerment namely**, the community is given space and voice in the tourism planning and policy-making process and increases participation in village development forums.

Community-Based Tourism (CBT) is a tourism model managed by and for local communities, with the goal of improving their well-being without damaging their culture and environment. Community-Based Tourism (CBT) plays a vital role in various aspects of social, economic, cultural, and environmental development. Maximizing village tourism potential is part of sustainable tourism development efforts. According to Pradana et. al. (2022) states that tourism development efforts in a broader context are part of sustainable development, which has become a global agenda in every development process. The role of Community-Based Tourism (CBT) includes improving the economic welfare of local communities, preserving local culture and traditions, protecting and conserving the environment, empowering communities socially, increasing local participation and ownership, and supporting the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In fact, one of the goals of community-based tourism is to realize sustainable tourism development. The study of Permatasari (2022) states that local communities play a crucial role in realizing sustainable tourism. The role of the government, regional governments, and tourism entrepreneurs is also crucial to realizing sustainable tourism. The success of Community-Based Tourism (CBT) depends heavily on the active participation and empowerment of local communities. With an inclusive approach, ongoing training, and support from stakeholders, Community-Based Tourism (CBT) can be an effective tool for equitable, sustainable, and locally-based development.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

Exploring potential coffee-based tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu used a descriptive qualitative method with a case study strategy. A descriptive qualitative approach is a research method for exploring and understanding the meanings that individuals or groups attach to social or humanitarian issues. Data collected is in the form of words, images, and not numbers (Kusumastuti & Khoiron, 2019). A case study is defined as a research strategy that involves an in-depth examination of a specific program, event, activity, process, or group of individuals. Each case has clear time and activity boundaries, and data is collected comprehensively through various information gathering techniques over a specific period (Kusumastuti & Khoiron, 2019). The case study in this

From Beans to Tourism: Exploring the Potential of Coffee-Based Tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu, Indonesia

research was conducted comparatively, comparing coffee tourism activities in Posong and Temanggung to understand the similarities and differences between the two coffee tourism locations in depth and contextually.

Data collection techniques were carried out through participant observation, focus group discussion, and literature studies. Participatory observation is an observation technique in which researchers participate in the field and observe the study subjects as the primary source of information. Researchers participate in social processes or situations, positioning themselves within the activities that occur, and observing the activities of those involved (Abdussamad, 2021). In this study, participant observation was conducted by participating in coffee tourism activities and observing the entire process, both in Posong and Tawangmangu. Focus group discussion and literature studies were then used to explore the perspectives of stakeholders involved in coffee tourism activities in both locations, strengthen field data, identify issues and opportunities relevant to coffee tourism development, and also serve as a tool to increase the validity of research findings (triangulation).

The data analysis technique used was thematic analysis. Braun & Clarke define thematic analysis as a data analysis method for identifying, analyzing, and interpreting patterns or themes within the data obtained. Thematic analysis was chosen because it allows researchers to systematically identify, organize, and interpret patterns of meaning (themes) that emerge from qualitative data. The analysis process was carried out through six stages: familiarization with the data, initial coding, theme search, theme review, defining and naming themes, and writing up the findings (Ahmed et. al., 2025).

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The data obtained were analyzed using thematic analysis through six steps: familiarization with the data, initial coding, theme discovery, theme review, defining and naming themes, and writing up the findings. During the familiarization stage, observation notes, discussions, and documentation studies were repeatedly read. The next stage involved manual initial coding to identify key pieces of data relevant to the research objectives. The coding included aspects of coffee cultivation practices, the role of local communities, and integration with ecotourism. These initial codes were then grouped into broad initial themes. The initial themes that emerged in this study were the natural potential of the two locations for coffee cultivation, local community involvement, and integrated tourism strategies. These initial themes were then reviewed and final themes were determined and named. The main themes identified in the study are as follows:

a. Potential and Characteristics of the Region: Posong and Tawangmangu

The potential and characteristics of coffee tourism areas in Posong, Temanggung Regency, and Sekipan, Tawangmangu District, Karanganyar Regency, are presented in the following table:

Table 1. Potential and Characteristics of the Region

Potential Aspects and Regional Characteristics	Posong, Temanggung	Sekipan, Tawangmangu
Geographical Conditions	Located on the slopes of Mount Sindoro at an altitude of $\pm 1,400$ – $1,600$ meters above sea level	Located on the slopes of Mount Lawu at an altitude of $\pm 1,200$ – $1,800$ meters above sea level
Characteristics of Local Coffee	Arabica coffee, cultivated in polyculture with tobacco	Arabica coffee (main), cultivated traditionally (planted under the shade of native trees, hand-picked, dried in the sun)
Natural Excellence	Panorama of Mount Sindoro and Mount Sumbing, a sunrise spot called the “golden sunrise” with a backdrop of eight mountains (Ungaran, Telomoyo, Andong, Lawu, Sindoro, Sumbing, Merbabu, and Merapi), fresh mountain air, located in the middle of a tobacco and coffee plantation area.	Hiking trails of Mount Lawu, beautiful natural scenery, fresh air, tea plantations, waterfalls (Grojogan Sewu, Jumog, Pringgodani), Sarangan Lake, Mongkrang Hill.
Local Culture	Traditional horse dance (<i>jathilan/kuda lumping</i>), mask dance, ritual traditions and traditional ceremonies	The village cleaning tradition "Julungan Ceremony" in Kalisoro Village, the chicken throwing tradition "Mondosiyo" in Kalisoro Village, feasts, joint prayers at ancestral shrines, cultural processions of community groups, <i>gamelan</i> and <i>reog</i> art performances

From Beans to Tourism: Exploring the Potential of Coffee-Based Tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu, Indonesia

Potential Aspects and Regional Characteristics	Posong, Temanggung	Sekipan, Tawangmangu
Agrotourism Activities	Camping, Glamour Camping (Glamping), trekking, cycling, culinary specialties, tour of Tlahab Tourism Village, educational tour of local Posong Coffee cultivation	Homestay, agrotourism, culinary, jeep tour, outbound, ornamental flower garden, coffee cafe with natural views
Community Support	Involvement of the Tlahab Village Government, Village Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) Bumi Arum Tlahab, local communities: Coffee SME activists, coffee farmers, local tourism managers	Involvement of coffee farmer groups under the management of Prohutani, local tourism managers
Accessibility	Paved road, ±30 minutes from downtown Temanggung, Central Java	Easy to reach, ±20–30 minutes from the center of Karanganyar, Central Java

Posong in Temanggung Regency and Sekipan in Tawangmangu District, Karanganyar Regency, are two mountainous areas in Central Java with significant potential for coffee-based tourism development. These two locations not only boast captivating landscapes and cool mountain air, but also possess socio-cultural characteristics that enhance the appeal of agrotourism.

Geographically, Posong is located on the slopes of Mount Sindoro at an altitude of approximately 1,400–1,600 meters above sea level, while Sekipan and Tawangmangu are located on the slopes of Mount Lawu at an altitude of approximately 1,200–1,800 meters above sea level. These conditions are very supportive for the cultivation of high-quality Arabica coffee. Posong develops a polyculture system between coffee and tobacco, while Sekipan maintains traditional cultivation methods that align with the concept of sustainable agriculture. In terms of natural advantages of each location, Posong has the advantage of panoramic views of Mount Sindoro and Sumbing and the "golden sunrise" with a backdrop of various mountains, while Sekipan and Tawangmangu offer a variety of ecotourism such as waterfalls and hiking trails of Mount Lawu. Viewed from a local cultural perspective, Posong is known for the traditional arts of *kuda lumping* and mask dance, while Sekipan and Tawangmangu have village cleaning traditions and traditional ceremonies rich in spiritual meaning and local wisdom.

Developing agrotourism activities in Posong include camping, trekking, coffee education tours, and village tours, while Sekipan offers homestay experiences, agrotourism, mountain climbing, and nature-based family activities. Local community involvement is a crucial pillar for sustainable tourism in both areas. In Posong, tourism management is supported by the Village Government, Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes), and coffee farming communities, including SME coffee businesses. In Sekipan and Tawangmangu, coffee farmer groups and the local Prohutani organization play an active role in developing the potential of coffee agrotourism. In terms of accessibility, both Posong and Tawangmangu are relatively easy to reach. Posong can be accessed within approximately 30 minutes from the center of Temanggung City, and Sekipan and Tawangmangu within approximately 20–30 minutes from the center of Karanganyar Regency.

Both locations possess geographic, ecological, and cultural characteristics that strongly support the development of coffee-based tourism. Both regions are situated in mountainous areas at ideal altitudes for Arabica coffee cultivation, and boast natural landscapes that are major tourist attractions. The uniqueness of local coffee, from its flavor and cultivation methods to polyculture practices, such as in Posong, which combines coffee with tobacco, is a key selling point, supporting the concept of authentic and sustainable coffee tourism. Furthermore, the richness of local culture, such as traditional ceremonies and local arts, strengthens the concept of experience-based tourism. This transforms coffee into more than just a commodity, but also a medium for cultural interpretation. Support from the local community and good accessibility from the district center also enhance social strength and facilitate destination development. Thus, the integration of nature, coffee, culture, and community in Posong and Tawangmangu makes both locations highly potential for the development of authentic, educational, and sustainable coffee-based tourism.

b. Coffee-Based Tourism Activities Already Underway: Community-Based Tourism (CBT)

In general, coffee-based tourism development in Posong and Tawangmangu has demonstrated quite diverse implementation, although it remains limited and requires strengthening in several aspects. In Posong, coffee-based tourism activities are integrated into nature and educational tourism packages offered by the Tlahab Tourism Village community. Tourists can take a coffee plantation tour, witness firsthand the coffee cultivation process carried out in polyculture with tobacco plants, and learn about environmentally friendly agricultural practices on the slopes of Mount Sindoro. Other activities offered include tasting Posong's signature coffee with a panoramic mountain backdrop. These activities are generally combined with camping and trekking packages. Educational tourism activities in the Tlahab Tourism Village are facilitated by the Village-Owned Enterprise (BUMDes), local coffee farmer groups, and coffee processing SMEs in Tlahab.

Meanwhile, in Sekipan and Tawangmangu, coffee-based tourism activities are being developed through a community empowerment approach, particularly local coffee farmers, who directly lead the innovation and management of the destinations. The coffee tourism model in Tawangmangu was pioneered by farmers through the "Lawu Coffee Cooperative," established in 2013 by 76 smallholder

From Beans to Tourism: Exploring the Potential of Coffee-Based Tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu, Indonesia

farmers. Their innovations include the development of homestays in traditional houses, coffee harvest participation packages for tourists, and demonstrations of coffee processing using traditional and modern methods. Furthermore, community capacity building is carried out through skills training such as quality control, cupping techniques, storytelling, basic English language skills, and financial management of tourism businesses. Empowerment efforts are also aimed at the younger generation through the Young Coffee Entrepreneurs program, which provides mentoring and micro-grants to establish new businesses, including cafes, guided tours, and digital marketing services. In several locations, coffee tourism activities are also combined with local customs and popular tourist destinations in Tawangmangu, such as Jumog Waterfall and Sarangan Lake, creating a comprehensive tourism experience. The coffee-based tourism activities that have been implemented in Posong, Temanggung, and Sekipan, Tawangmangu, demonstrate strong alignment with the Community-Based Tourism (CBT) approach, where local communities play a key role in the direct management and utilization of tourism resources. In Posong, coffee tourism has been developed through the active involvement of the Tlahab Village community. Coffee farmer groups, SMEs, and Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) are at the forefront of implementing coffee-based educational tourism. In this context, the community is not only the recipient of economic benefits but also serves as a service provider, guide, and guardian of local values. This reflects the main principles of CBT: community empowerment and local control over decision-making. Scheyvens & van der Watt (2021) argue that empowerment is at the heart of CBT, where local communities are given control over the planning, management, and distribution of tourism benefits. Meanwhile, in Tawangmangu, coffee tourism activities are developing in a format that also emphasizes community participation. Local communities that are members of the Prohutani Coffee Farmers Group and the Lawu Coffee Cooperative manage coffee plantations and provide access for tourists to experience firsthand the process of traditional and modern coffee cultivation, integration with local culture, and the development of homestays managed by the community to provide space for tourists to interact directly with community life. This is in accordance with the CBT principle regarding meaningful social interactions between tourists and local residents. In line with the opinion of Rong-Da Liang et. al. (2023) that co-creation in CBT, which involves the direct participation of local communities as hosts, guides, and facilitators, creates an authentic tourism experience and strengthens interactions between tourists and local residents.

These two regions demonstrate that coffee-based tourism practices focus not only on the commodity or the coffee consumption experience, but also serve as an instrument for strengthening the local economy, preserving culture, and fostering sustainable development. With a strong participatory structure and community involvement at every stage, coffee tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu can be categorized as a form of community-based tourism that is inclusive, sustainable, and based on local potential.

c. Potential for Product Integration and Diversification

Coffee tourism development in Posong and Tawangmangu has significant potential for integrated development through cross-sector integration and product diversification. This integration can expand the value chain, enhance destination appeal, and provide broader economic benefits to local communities.

Table 2. Potential for Integration and Diversification of Coffee-Based Tourism Products in Posong and Tawangmangu

Category	Potential	Explanation/Example
Tour Package Integration	Educational and Participatory Tourism	Coffee plantation tours, harvesting with farmers, cupping, annual coffee festival, coffee education for schools, plantation tours for students, organic farming education for students and international tourists
	Natural and Cultural Tourism	Garden trekking, camping, climbing, sunrise/sunset spots, visits to traditional sites, local art performances, harvest ceremonies
	Religious Tourism	The potential for integrating visits to local religious sites as part of the village cultural narrative
Tourism Product Development	Coffee Themed Homestay	Stay at a farmer's house, experience village life and get to know coffee from upstream to downstream
	Interactive Workshop	Coffee roasting, brewing, and storytelling training; hands-on activities for tourists; coffee seminars
	Annual Coffee Festival	Local coffee promotion events, MSME bazaars, local barista competitions, and cultural performances. Examples include the "Tawangmangu Coffee Fest" held July 26-27,

From Beans to Tourism: Exploring the Potential of Coffee-Based Tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu, Indonesia

Category	Potential	Explanation/Example
		2025, a Manual Brewing Competition, and the sale of brewed coffee.
	Thematic Agrotourism	Agrotourism packages “one-day farmer experience” and “coffee and local culture”, a combination of coffee and tobacco in Posong
Product Diversification (Tawangmangu)	Coffee Processed Products	Honey coffee, coffee-based snacks: coffee-flavored <i>getuk</i> (cassava cake) and <i>wingko babat</i> (coconut cake), aromatic coffee
	Creative Products	Coffee tree wood crafts, colored textiles from coffee cherry pulp
Product Diversification (Posong)	Coffee and Tobacco	Posong Coffee, education on intercropping coffee and tobacco farming patterns
	Creative and Educational Products Packaging	Educational tourism packaging or souvenirs with local wisdom stories about coffee farmers in Posong and narratives of Tlahab Village

From an integration perspective, both regions have strong potential to develop educational and participatory tourism packages. This potential can be optimized by integrating nature tourism activities such as garden walks and hiking with cultural and religious tourism, such as visits to traditional sites or village ceremonies, and educational activities targeting both local students and international tourists. Activities such as coffee education for schools, garden tours for students, and education about coffee and the environment can provide sustainable additional attractions.

Tourism product development opportunities are also abundant, including coffee-themed homestay packages, interactive workshops on coffee processing (from roasting, brewing, to cupping), and annual coffee festivals that involve farmers, MSMEs, and tourists in a celebration of local coffee. Furthermore, the development of coffee-based thematic agrotourism can also enrich the tourist experience. Examples include agrotourism packages with themes such as "one-day farmer experience" and "coffee and local culture."

In terms of product diversification, Tawangmangu has demonstrated innovative practices in creating coffee-derived products such as honey coffee, coffee-based snacks, crafts made from coffee tree wood, and even textiles dyed with coffee cherry pulp. This diversification not only expands the potential of the creative economy but also strengthens the narrative of sustainability and locality in tourism. Meanwhile, in Posong, product diversification is demonstrated through the integration of coffee and tobacco as part of an intercropping system. This has resulted in a distinctive coffee product that embodies the narrative of the local wisdom of farmers on the slopes of Sindoro: “Posong Coffee”. Furthermore, there is potential for developing coffee product diversification in the form of packaging or educational tourism souvenirs, which incorporate local wisdom, stories of coffee and tobacco farmers in Posong and narratives of Tlahab Village in each package. By optimizing product integration and diversification, coffee tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu will not only have a unique and authentic experiential appeal but will also be able to form an inclusive, creative, and sustainable tourism ecosystem.

d. Challenges and Recommended Development Strategies

Indonesia is known as one of the world's top coffee producers, boasting a diverse range of coffee varieties and flavors across its regions. Beyond its reputation as a leading commodity, coffee also holds significant potential for development as a tourist attraction through the concept of agrotourism, or coffee-based tourism. This tourism not only offers the experience of enjoying coffee but also provides education, interaction with farmers, and exploration of the local culture inherent in coffee cultivation. However, coffee tourism faces several challenges in its development, ranging from inadequate infrastructure to a lack of skilled human resources in the tourism sector. Therefore, appropriate strategies are needed to ensure sustainable coffee-based tourism growth and provide economic, social, and environmental benefits to local communities.

Coffee-based tourism development in areas such as Posong (Temanggung, Central Java) and Tawangmangu (Karanganyar, Central Java) holds significant potential due to their geographic and cultural characteristics that support coffee cultivation and natural tourist attractions. However, challenges remain, and strategies are recommended for development. Generally, these challenges include limited infrastructure, a lack of trained human resources, inadequate branding and promotion, unintegrated management, and dependence on the harvest season. Based on these challenges, recommended development strategies include improving tourism infrastructure, empowering local human resources, strengthening branding and promotion, diversifying tourism products, strengthening institutions and collaboration, and developing sustainable ecotourism.

From Beans to Tourism: Exploring the Potential of Coffee-Based Tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu, Indonesia

Table 3. Challenges and Strategies for Developing Coffee Tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu

Challenges	Development Strategy Recommendations
Limited local human resource capacity (especially in hospitality, marketing, and foreign languages)	Ongoing training for farmers and residents (roasting, guiding, storytelling, hospitality) Foreign language and digital marketing capacity building programs through partnerships with universities or NGOs
Supporting infrastructure is not yet optimal	Improvement of road and transportation infrastructure to tourist locations, including tourist information points through collaboration between local governments and BUMDes or local communities.
Lack of digital promotion and market networking	Strengthening destination branding based on local narratives Digital content creation and integrated promotion through social media, travel marketplaces, and travel platform partnerships
Challenges in maintaining the sustainability of the local environment and culture	Implementation of sustainable tourism principles (eco-tourism): limiting the number of visitors, waste management, tourist education Tourism activities are linked to cultural preservation, such as harvest ceremonies, local arts, and coffee folklore.
Dependence on harvest season (seasonal)	Diversification of tourism activities outside the harvest season (workshops, cultural tours, forest therapy, annual coffee festival) Innovation in processed coffee products that can be sold all year round
Unintegrated tourism management	Establishment of cross-actor forums, preparation of coffee tourism village master plans, and training on integrated destination management.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The findings in this article indicate that coffee tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu has significant potential for development as a form of nature, culture, and community-based tourism. Posong and Tawangmangu have strong potential for coffee-based tourism development thanks to a combination of favorable geographic, ecological, and cultural characteristics. Their mountainous locations, unique local coffee varieties, cultivation practices such as polyculture, and rich cultural traditions make them suitable for authentic and sustainable coffee tourism. Community support and good accessibility also strengthen the competitiveness of these destinations as models of educational and experiential coffee-based tourism. Coffee tourism activities in Posong and Tawangmangu demonstrate the strong application of Community-Based Tourism (CBT) principles, where local communities play a key role in management, service provision, and cultural preservation. In Posong, BUMDes and coffee farmer groups are actively involved in educational tourism, while in Tawangmangu, cooperatives and farmer groups provide access to coffee tourism based on direct interaction and local culture. Challenges that need to be addressed in developing coffee tourism in Posong and Tawangmangu include limited local human resources, suboptimal infrastructure, lack of digital promotion, sustainability challenges, dependence on harvest seasons, and non-integrated management. Recommended development strategies include ongoing training, infrastructure improvements, strengthening local branding, implementing ecotourism principles, diversifying tourism activities and products, and establishing collaborative forums for integrated governance.

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